

Evaluation process in the application of Case Teaching Method in Management education: a study in the perception of professors from Brazilian universities

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Abstract

Active methodologies allow the use of evaluation formats that cover weaknesses of current evaluation methods (Mansur & Alves, 2018). As for teaching cases, Dalfovo (2013) and Ribeiro (2016) discuss the lack of systematic assessment. The work aims to understand the evaluation process in the application of the case method in management courses at Brazilian universities, with specific objectives: to describe the planning process in the application of learning evaluation; investigate the adoption of instruments and strategies used in case evaluation for teaching; identify the monitoring adopted in the evaluation and identify a suggestion for improvement from the data of the evaluation carried out with the students. This is a multiple and exploratory case study. A semi-structured interview script was applied with management professors from two Brazilian universities. The data were discussed from the qualitative approach adopting content analysis. The results of the research are similar to the studies on evaluation in teaching methods, although none of them is the method of the case. All teachers surveyed carry out planning, corroborating the studies by Silva, Santos & Paixão (2014). Some teachers value the moment of the evaluation, elaborating the teaching plan (Tormena & Figueiredo, 2010). Otherwise, the group plans to value the forms of evaluation adopted (Fernandes & Fialho, 2012). Regarding assessment instruments (Depresbiteris & Tavares, 2009), most teachers use student observation. In the monitoring of the evaluation, a large part of it does so through group discussions (Depresbiteris & Tavares, 2017). With the results of the evaluation, most teachers perceive the need for the student to know the theory to associate the content with the resolution of the case (Miranda, 2008). The findings of the work are the different ways of planning, the observation of groups as an assessment tool, as well as the follow-up of discussions, based on these observations and the importance of theory for solving the case.

Keywords: Method Case; Evaluation; Learning; Management Education.

1 Introduction

The manager's work pace makes his practice less reflective (Mintzberg, 2010). This reality is also a reflection of teaching historically based only on reproducing and had to transform itself so that the professional develops the skills of understanding, critical analysis and reflection in a competitive market (Suaia, 2013, Kakouris, 2015). In this context, Silva, Oliveira and Mota (2013) points out the case of the method of teaching as one of the learning system in action strategies for management education. From the practice of methodologies such as the case for teaching, it is also necessary to apply other forms of assessment that can cover the weaknesses of the assessment methods applied until then (Mansur & Alves, 2018).

In this sense, this article aims to understand the process of learning assessment with the application of the case method for teaching in Brazilian administration courses and specific objectives: (i) Describe the planning process for the application of learning assessment; (ii) Investigate the adoption of instruments and strategies used in the evaluation process; (iii) Identify the monitoring and control mechanisms adopted in the evaluation and; (iv) identify a suggestion for improvement from the data of the evaluation carried out with the students, when they applied the cases for teaching.

Despite the research being carried out in the Administration context, the study has a relevant contribution to Engineering, since Administrative Science has, in its curriculum, contents and curricular units, transversal

disciplines, when compared to the Engineering area. Thus, a study of Administration in an Engineering meeting becomes relevant mainly to generate a discussion about the need to contemplate transdisciplinary contents aimed also at developing Engineering students, as well as in Administration area, the technical skills, attitudes and abilities necessary to lead people and work teams, so important for both careers..

2 Case Method for teaching and the learning assessment process

Gil (2004) conceptualizes the case method for teaching as reports used and studied by individuals or groups to solve problems and make decisions. For Araujo, Rejowsky and Leal (2012), it is a methodology that describes a real problem faced by a person in the organization, usually presented from the point of view of the decision maker, in order to take this situation to a learning context, inviting people and students to reflect and position themselves in the context presented. The case teaching method can be named as many variables: case study method, case-based learning, case method for teaching, but still carrying the same meaning and being related to the same active methodology.

To Burgoyne & Mumford (2001) the Case Teaching Method in management education and development is the most used approach outside the traditional lecture/instruction format. For the student to be able to position himself and put himself in the role of the decision maker to find the solution to the problem presented, it is necessary that he has sufficient theoretical foundation to apply theory to practice and solve the problem presented, avoiding the risk of be based on 'beliefs' (Christense, 1987)

Miranda (2008), when studying the evaluation of learning through teaching cases in graduate courses in business, describes the learning process in three stages: a) individual preparation of the student: familiarization reading, complementary readings, diagnosis of the problem, development of alternatives, definition of criteria, proposal of solution; b) group discussion (Mendes, Trevisan & Souza, 2016), where there is an opportunity to debate individual positions and advance the level of understanding; c) plenary discussion, where the understanding of the case develops.

Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the importance of planning and carrying out the work proposed by the teacher. One of the ways to carry out this planning is from the preparation of the teaching plan built at the beginning of the discipline (Silva, Santos & Paixão, 2014). The plan helps the teacher to organize the necessary resources for the classes and favors the monitoring of the activities that will be developed (Tormena & Figueiredo, 2010). This avoids improvisation, facilitates the integration of students with learning experiences, so that the student's vision is broadened, cooperative, participatory and he develops autonomy in learning (Sasaki, 1997, Nogaro, 2018)

To put into practice the forms of assessment, the professor should make use of assessment tools to assist in their practice, diversifying forms of collect accurate information and carry out analysis and interpretation in order to improve the process of learning (Depresbiteris & Tavares, 2017, Haydt, 2002). Once the assessment instruments are applied, the professor is able to monitor the development of the student's learning process. Dalfavo (2013) & Ribeiro (2016) draw attention to the difficulties encountered by teachers in evaluating students when applying cases for teaching. One of the ways to carry out this monitoring, for example, is through the observation of group discussions, when the case is applied. For Depresbiteris and Tavares (2017) and Mendes, Trevisan and Souza (2016), group observation must be systematic and planned so that the teacher has the amount of information necessary to assess the student's level of learning.

3 Methodology

This is a multiple and exploratory case study, with a qualitative analysis approach. In this perspective, the present study investigates the perception of professors from UFRN and UFPB who use the case method for teaching in their disciplines. Four professors from UFRN were interviewed personally and five professors from UFPB through skype meetings, during September to December 2019.

Data processing was carried out through content analysis, where the categories of analysis emerged from theoretical support: evaluation planning (Silva, Santos & Paixão, 2014), evaluation instruments and strategies (Depresbiteris & Tavares, 2009), monitoring of the evaluation (Depresbiteris & Tavares, 2017) and actions taken after the evaluation (Miranda, 2008).

Finally, for data analysis, the transcribed comments of the interview were read, with the objective of coding and grouping the text units, comparing them with those categories already identified in the theory.

4 Analysis of Results

In order to maintain the anonymity of the respondents, a codification was established for the subjects and their speeches, distinguishing them between participants from Rio Grande do Norte and Paraíba. In this way, the code "P" represents that the respondent is the professor, as in UFRN four professors were interviewed, the codes varied from being from P1 to P4, on the other hand, among the UFPB professors, which were five, the codes ranged from P5 to P9.

The acronyms RN were added to the end of the professors' codes, to facilitate the identification of professors in Rio Grande do Norte and professors in Paraíba - PB. At the end of the initials of each professor's status, codes ranging from f1 to f4 were also established to represent the participants' statements.

The first question of the interview script sought to identify how the teacher planned the assessment of learning in the application of cases for teaching in the discipline taught. The results of the interviews carried out demonstrate that all professors interviewed at UFRN and UFPB carry out the planning, in some way, of the case evaluation process for applied teaching in the classroom.

The teachers' response corroborates the studies by Silva, Santos and Paixão (2014), who carried out their research with the assessment of learning in general. This study is used to compare with the results found here, because in the research found on teaching cases, there are no registers of teachers who planned evaluation when using this methodology.

The authors point out that a survey carried out among professors of the Administration course, all the teachers interviewed carry out the planning of the academic semester, including in it the evaluations performed. Planning is presented to the students and discussed in class, even if students do not engage in an active way, the intention is to clarify the what will be covered in class.

Thus, and according to the supported studies, planning serves as a guide to lead teachers during the development period of the discipline, helping to achieve the learning objectives. In this way, the teacher does not run over the content and follows the calendar to guide the course of the classes.

Therefore, it is understood that the teacher who plans his evaluations is able to organize his work in advance for the duration of the classes and to apply the evaluative activities at the appropriate moments in the classroom, avoiding improvisations and being able to accompany his students during the process of learning.

The planning of the evaluation is carried out in two ways by the teachers surveyed: a first group that carries out from the moment of the evaluation, using the teaching plan (Sasaki, 1997, Nogaro, 2018) and a second group that focuses on the forms of evaluation, valuing student participation in small groups and in plenary (Tormena & Figueiredo, 2010). The results of the research are similar to the studies by Sasaki (1997) and Tormena and Figueiredo (2010) although these refer to evaluation methods in general. They are also close to the research of Nogaro (2018) that refer to the assessment of learning when using problem-based learning. The statements of the following subjects refer to the teachers of the first group.

"I usually deliver a lesson plan, where they already know the days they have activity because I score all of them, you know, I don't just do tests, I like to do continuous assessment and I use the case not only to bring the student closer to the practice, but I also do an evaluation with him. [...] The planning is always prior." (Ppb7F1)

"They know, oh, you'll be evaluated like this, they know everything, the whole process, before, well before, they don't know before, they know well before, they know the whole evaluation process and how much the case will weigh in their evaluation in the discipline's learning process. They know everything so as not to have improvisations." (Ppb5F1)

The reports showed that they value the importance of planning carried out *a priori* in relation to methodological choices and evaluations carried out during the course of the disciplines. Teachers' statements confirm the results of research carried out by Sasaki (1997), Nogaro (2018) when they state that planning is necessary, thus avoiding improvisation and facilitating the integration of students with learning experiences.

From this, the moment the teacher makes the prior planning of his classes, the research teacher chooses the most appropriate evaluation method that he will use for each moment of the discipline, according to the programmed content and, he passes this information on to the students. The subjects' speeches strengthen their concern with regard to anticipating the planning of activities because they understand the importance of caring for the educational process and the training of professionals. The act of training requires the teacher to anticipate questions such as: what do you intend to develop in students' learning? What skills and how to achieve them? How to attain the learning objectives?

According to the studies pointed out in this work, when teachers present to students the planning of classes that contain the evaluative activities that will be performed, this attitude may be related to the need to avoid improvisation, since it is known what will happen in classroom, thus assisting in the quality of student learning. In addition, when teachers reinforce in the testimonies, for example, "they already know the days when they have activity" and "They know everything", these statements demonstrate that for them, prior communication with the student is also a relevant parameter.

Unlike the perception of this first group of teachers, the second group values the forms of assessment they will adopt in the classroom, that is, they did not detail the time period in which they planned the assessments, but described the type of assessment they adopt when applying the teaching cases. In this way, when discussing the forms of assessment, teachers also address the strategies used when performing assessment in the classroom. Most teachers, therefore, report that they perform based on student participation in small groups and then expand the debate to a large group discussion, as can be seen in the excerpts of the statements below.

"[...] then students can discuss in groups and then we take a larger approach with the whole room and then I make theoretical connections and clarify some concepts" (Prn2F1).

"[...] we do the discussion in small groups and then do the discussion in the plenary." (Ppb10F1)

"[...] they divide it into groups, they debate the answers in groups and then, they get the whole group together so that we can arrive more or less at a common denominator, more or less." (Ppb6F1)

"[...] to what extent the case solutions developed by groups of students, I never worked individually, I worked in groups, to what extent the answers offered by the groups to the dilemmas of the cases involved the effective use of literature that was being presented." (Ppb8F1)

"At first, the participation of students and their involvement in small groups, right? When we separate the class, go to the groups and pass the questions, pass the case and pass the questions. So I evaluate the interaction between them, you see the participation of everyone, round between the groups observing the interaction, participation and contribution, right. This is a first step. In the second moment it makes a large group and then again I evaluate the general participation group by group and individually in the solution of the issues." (Ppb9F1)

In the reports presented by the teachers, it is clear that they prefer to adopt an assessment considering the student's participation in the case discussions, both in small groups and in the plenary discussion, so that the student himself can interact, argue and discuss the solutions of the case and learn during the debates.

The excerpts from the speeches corroborate the studies by Miranda (2008) who point out that in discussions in small groups and in plenary there is an opportunity to debate individual positions and advance the level of

complete and detailed understanding of the case. In this way, when the teacher describes the student's participation in the discussions using this to evaluate him, according to what the studies present, he helps the student to position himself in the discussions, to place himself as the decision maker, reflecting on the problem and understanding the situation presented.

Still in relation to execution, there was another question in the interview script that aimed to discover the instruments and strategies used by the teacher when assessing learning when applying cases for teaching in the discipline taught. The reports show that the majority of professors at UFRN and UFPB carry out the assessment based on observation, which has subjective characteristics.

The studies by Depresbiteris and Tavares (2009), when researching evaluation in general, assure that the instruments are used as tools to collect information about student learning and can be diverse, such as: tests, case analysis, map conceptual, portfolios, situational evidence, operational evidence and several others. For the authors, the diversification of instruments is important because it gives the possibility to analyze students' learning from different angles. The subjects' statements point out that,

"[...] I usually observe in fact, because as I understand that the case is the moment to generate only reflections, discussions, which is not right or wrong, right from the answers, each one has their own way of manage and solve problems." (Ppb9F2)

"[...] as the case he has this peculiarity of not having a single answer, it is important to observe how the students behave because they like cases a lot, it is very interesting to see" (Ppb10F3)

"No, I never used assessment tools. (Pp b8F2) [...] I did not use criteria that were objective, no scales or tables that aimed, it was much more in the sense of how creative or how inventive [...] how plausible the solutions were"(Ppb8F1)

"Usually I make a qualitative judgment, I take the characterization of what was produced and I make the judgment in relation to density, depth. [...] it is more in the qualitative perspective of me as a judge to observe if that provision makes sense, does not make sense and under what conditions it is being treated "(Prn4F2).

"I rate according to what the class is going on. I don't use an instrument and now at that moment in each case I don't. I have some skills that I want, for example, that they develop, for example, part of teamwork in interpersonal relationships, it is an interesting skill that they work in the classroom. So I observe this, I see how it will flow"(Prn2F2)

So this group of teachers prefer to evaluate students based on the observation strategy, so that they follow the evolution of the learning of these students in the classroom. These results also showed that teachers evaluate students during the entire development process and not just performing assessments in a timely manner.

According to Depresbiteris and Tavares (2017), observation must be systematic and planned so that we have rich information. For this to happen, observation needs to occur throughout the entire learning process. In this same direction, Haydt's (2002) studies conclude that the more data the teacher collects and records about the student in his observation, the more condition he will have to make an accurate analysis of his performance.

Therefore, it is believed that, from the studies described, teachers who use observation as an evaluation strategy are able to follow the evolution of students' learning throughout the entire process in the classroom, without resorting only to traditional assessments. Accredited ta also that when the teacher performs this monitoring, gives the student more safety without need to be evaluating the tension in just a moment, as the realization of an event, for example.

Teachers were also asked about the monitoring and control mechanisms adopted in the learning assessment process. The reports show that the majority of professors at UFRN and UFPB somehow carry out the monitoring of students' learning assessment through group discussions, based on observations.

"I follow the groups as they discuss and talk about the answers." (Ppb9F3)

"[...] we don't intervene in his resolution, we follow the discussions and see how they are working in a group" (Prn1F3)

"[...] I go around the groups, observe the most interesting comments and follow the discussions." (Prn2F3)

"[...] participation in groups and engagement in activities, I observe participation, engagement and the performance of these activities for me has become much more important than the mere bureaucratic issue, reading and discussing, reading and discussing, read and discuss "(Ppb8F3)

"And then, in small groups, I'm already taking my notes, right, when I go past them, I'm already watching the discussions." (Ppb5F3)

"[...] I really visit the teams and follow the discussions" (Ppb7F3)

Teachers follow the students' evaluation process by visiting the small groups formed in the classroom and observing their discussions regarding the problem proposed in the case.

The studies by Mendes, Trevisan and Souza (2016) show that the teacher, when observing his students' group work, can generate information that will serve to support decisions related to the teaching and learning processes. These observations, even if they are mere impressions captured by the teacher during a lesson, can provide a very complete picture of the learning process.

The authors also point out that observing the student's activity involves paying attention: the level of solution sought for the task, the types of mistakes made, their collaboration with classmates, their need for support, their suggestions, the emotional aspects, motivation and concentration

It is understood, according to the studies mentioned, that the teachers observe the participation and engagement of students in the groups and make the necessary notes to accompany the learning process. This monitoring becomes important so that, in addition to observing the participation of each student in the discussions, the teacher can verify the student's development in the proposed activity, realizing the difficulties encountered by the students, helping, guiding them so that they can achieve the goal of study.

Another question was asked to the teachers now related to a suggestion that they would make from the data of the evaluation carried out with the students, when they applied the cases for teaching. Most professors at UFRN and UFPB replied that they reinforce with students the importance of using theory as an important tool for solving the case.

"I realized that the students in the resolution had learned very little about HR practices, for example, then I said, look, now we are going to redo a reprogramming here, because we failed in this aspect, we needed theoretical support in this, right, so as they were unable to rescue what they studied there, I was able to reinforce it. " (Ppb5F4)

"[...] we are always reinforcing the use of the theoretical foundation, we ask the student to read and have the theoretical foundation and then he will test [...] why this foundation and theorist when it is put to solve practical situations he manages to develop technical competence. "(Prn1F4)

"[...] it's important to know the theory because without an instrument, you can't walk. Stay in that empty managerial speech that you think is an untrained administrator. " (Prn4F4)

"[...] if they managed to make associations with the content seen in the classroom, the theory, right? If we managed to work this well." (Ppb6F4)

Teachers recognize as an important action to strengthen for students the discourse that they need to know the theory that is supporting the case so that they can have enough elements to discuss the proposed problems and provide solutions. Christensen (1987) suggests, therefore, in his studies that the discussions are based on the point of view of management theories so that there is no risk that students will argue based only on common sense or 'guesswork', but be based on the suitable theories for such a subject.

Wherefore, It is understood that the theories that support the performance of activities must be clear for the learning process to happen. In this way, the student will be able to demonstrate how they have developed the necessary skills to achieve the learning objectives. When there is an approximation with the theory, the student has the opportunity to apply it in real world situations, positioning himself as the decision maker, corroborating with the studies of Marion and Marion (2006). The authors also point out that when Professor Prn1F4 reinforces in his testimony that the student will "have the theoretical foundation and then he will test" and "he is placed to solve practical situations", these statements demonstrate that he considers the theory important for the student develops the necessary skills in his training as an administrator.

5 Conclusion

The result of the research showed that professors who consider the moment of planning important, value the preparation of the teaching plan and thinking about the evaluation in advance because they value the importance of their teaching and the responsibility committed to training administrator. At the same time, there are those who consider the forms of assessment used to explain the planning of activities. This may be related to the fact that the teacher has the planning activity already normalized, which already does so involuntarily. It was also identified that most teachers evaluate their students based on the observation of groups in the classroom, which take into account the student's autonomy in their learning process. As well as the monitoring of the evaluation, which takes place from the discussions promoted in groups, occurs.

Pursuant to, this process invites the student to reflect and position himself in the discussions, developing the skills and competencies to achieve the learning objectives developed by the teacher. However, in order for the student to have the security of conducting group discussions, the teachers interviewed report that it is necessary that they approach the theories required to solve the dilemma reported in the case.

The study does not intend to make generalizations, nor does it intend to serve as a unique path to be followed by teachers and institutions. Thus, it seeks to serve as a source of comparison and inspiration, generating possibilities for new research, reflections and discussions related to the difficulties and challenges that teachers already have in relation to evaluation and that they face when applying a new pedagogical model .

Finally, it can be pointed out as a weak point of the study the difficulty of carrying out the research with the professors due to the unavailability of time, which led to the need to extend the term of completion of this study. As suggestions for further studies, research based on the results found is recommended, expand on the sample size of participants in the analysis, as well as, using quantitative research methods, and yet relating them to the students' perception of the application of learning assessment when using the case method, comparing them with the results found here.

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6 References

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